

The Third Half: training and upskilling Early Career Researchers in well-being and positive mental health at the Autonomous University of Barcelona

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Purpose

In response to the alarming reports before and after the pandemic regarding the decreasing levels of wellbeing among early career researchers (ECR; Kiskmihok et al., 2021; Levecque et al., 2017), a pilot study called The Third Half (Muro et al., 2022) was performed at the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB) during the first semester of 2022. It was aimed to analyze the efficacy of an innovative and evidence-based training for upskilling in wellbeing. Pilot 2022 results showed that the training increased emotional wellbeing and decreased psychological distress of the participants, but some methodological issues (i.e.: sample size or lack of control group) made it hard to generalize results. Nevertheless, as results were encouraging, the Doctoral School decided to implement of the Third Half as an optional and certified activity for doctoral candidates during this academic year 2022-23. Accordingly, the present study was designed to analyze the efficacy of the new Third Half implementation at the UAB in a larger sample of ECR, including a control group

Design

This is a quasi-experimental study with an intervention and a control group using a pre-test and a post-test design.

Population and Sample

The sample consists of 101 doctoral students (62.5% women) of which 41 are part of the experimental group and 60 of the control group.

Intervention

The Third Half program consists of 6 sessions of 3 hours each, and is culturally adapted to the social context of doctoral students.

In the intervention group, a program structured by the five major criteria from evidence-based practices for the promotion of well-being is carried out:

- Exposure to outdoor green spaces
- Physical activity
- Gamification
- Mentoring
- Positive psychology and coaching techniques

Measurement

A brief survey was designed to explore the sociodemographic profile of the participants, their mental health, including measures of well-being and psychological distress and finally, we also assessed their personality traits. Other ad-hoc items were included to evaluate their satisfaction with the doctoral training process. The survey was sent to doctoral students through an e-mail from the Doctoral School requesting their participation. Different valid and reliable questionnaires, widely used in research on mental health, were administered:

- a. Brief Emotional Profiles Scale (Profile of Mood States-POMS; Andrade et al., 2013).
- b. General Anxiety Disorder -7 (GAD7; García et al., 2010).
- c. Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ9; Kroenke et al., 2001).
- d. Well-Being Index-WBI (WHO-5; World Health Organization, 1998)
- e. The Big Five Inventory -2 Extra-Short Form (BFI-2-XS; Soto and John, 2017).
- f. Additionally, 5 ad-hoc items were designed to ascertain levels of motivation (including motivation with the thesis, perceived motivation from the supervisor and from the team), relationship with the supervisor, and satisfaction with the doctoral training process.
- g. Finally, 2 items were included to know the health status of the doctoral students, asking if they suffer from any chronic or acute illness.

Two measurements will be made in both the intervention and control group. The first one before the implementation of the program and the second measurement after the end of the program.

Statistical Analysis

The information will be analyzed using the IBM-SPSS 24.0 program, initially a descriptive univariate analysis of the study variables will be performed, internal consistency will be

calculated using Cronbach's alpha test (1951) in the two measurements: first pre-test measurement and second post-test measurement. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (also K-S test) will be used to determine the behavior of the distribution of the study variables. In the case of obtaining variables that meet the criteria for the use of parametric statistical tests, the following analyses will be carried out:

Comparisons of the means of sociodemographic characteristics at baseline in the intervention and control groups will be performed with Student's t-tests for quantitative variables and odds ratios (OR), with 95% confidence interval (95%CI).

A Student's t test will be applied to establish comparisons of the variable scores between the intervention and control groups or F test (manova) for comparisons of the scores in the two measurements. Differences showing probability values of less than 5% ($p < 0.05$) will be accepted as significant. If necessary, adjustments will be made for possible confounding demographic variables in the most appropriate statistical tests according to the type of variable.

Ethical Considerations

The project has been approved by the Comitè Ètic d'Experimentació Animal i Humana from the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) with the reference code: CEEAH 6007. This study adopts the ethical aspects of the Declaration of Helsinki. In order to participate in the study, a signed informed consent was needed by the doctoral students. The respect, integrity, and safety of the participants is preserved. The team in charge of the implementation of the program is composed of health professionals with experience in interventions and will use questionnaires that do not imply a risk to the mental health of the doctoral students participating in the study.

Results (if applicable)

The present project is now being implemented and two of the six proposed sessions have already been carried out; it is expected to be completed in the second week of May. As a result, all the data will be collected and analyzed by the time of the conference. Within the expected results, it is intended to find significant increases in participants mental health, this is, enhanced well-being and decreased psychological distress (Muro et al., 2022).

Implications

Positive pilot results encourage further research and suggest how important it is for the academic community the implementation and evaluation of evidence-based psychological programs to support the mental health of researchers toward creating healthier workplaces among doctoral communities (Muro et al., 2022).

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